

Bringing in the New Year

📅 8 MONTHS AGO ⌚ READ TIME:3MINUTES 👤 BY WP_11035540 💬 LEAVE A COMMENT

By Brendan Dooley

Mediceo del Principato, vol. 2861. Unpaginated, but bound tightly enough so as not to confuse the order of pages. Leafing through, we find the order of pages seems somewhat idiosyncratic. Why is "From Bruxelles the 20th of December 1614" followed by "From Genoa, 9 January 1614," although the progression of dates up to 20 December otherwise seems perfectly chronological?

Did the compiler of the volume blink while sorting and binding the pages? More probably, he sorted the pages according to early modern criteria regarding the start of the year– which did not always occur on the first of January!

In fact, until the eighteenth century numerous systems were in use, of which the following is a short list:

NATIVITY STYLE sets the first day of the year to December 25th.

INCARNATION STYLE sets the first day of the year to 25 March, used in Tuscany until 1749, and elsewhere

VENETO STYLE , is fixed on March 1st

BYZANTINE STYLE According to this style, the year begins on September 1st

CIRCUMCISION STYLE is the current system, although in fact, well before that time, the Julian calendar stipulated for the year to begin on January 1st.

Looking at the same archival volume (2861) a little further on in January: The writer apparently can't decide! He's put in 1614 and corrected it to 1615 (or, did he put 1615 and, for a scruple about attachment to older styles of dating, correct it to 1614?).

Here:

calendar in Ireland, 1583-1782" (unpublished paper at "Ireland, Rome and the Holy See: History, Culture and Contact," a UCC History Department symposium at the Pontifical Irish College, Rome, 1 April 2006), https://www.academia.edu/209971/The_Popes_new_invention_the_introduction_of_the_Gregorian_calendar_in_Ireland_1583_1782?source=swp_share consulted on Jan. 26, 2022

B. Dooley, Introduction, in B. Dooley, ed., *The Dissemination of News and the Emergence of Contemporaneity in Early Modern Europe* (Ashgate, 2010).